

Mini review

Macrophage polarization and infectious diseases

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Summary. Macrophages are a heterogeneous cell population present in most mammalian tissues with a wide range of functions. They are an essential component of optimal tissue homeostasis and an essential first line of defense against pathogens. Activated macrophages are typically divided into two phenotypes, M1 macrophages and M2 macrophages, which are influenced by microorganisms, the tissue microenvironment, and cytokine signals from physiological conditions to infections. The management of macrophage polarity is crucial for the prevention and treatment of infections and inflammatory disorders. In this review, we will evaluate the current state of knowledge regarding macrophage polarity and discuss how pathogens exploit macrophage phenotypes for efficient replication and disease progression.

Keywords: macrophage polarization, M1 macrophages, M2 macrophages, pathogens.

INTRODUCTION

Macrophages are specialized, tissue-resident phagocytic cells of the innate immune system. They were first observed in 1892 by a Russian zoologist, Ilya Metchnikov, in an experiment where he introduced a rose torn into the body of a starfish larvae and observed the accumulation of phagocytes attempting to devour the foreign material (Yona and Gordon 2015). For his work in immunology, Metchnikov was awarded in 1908 the Nobel Prize for Physiology or Medicine together with Paul Ehrlich, both of whom are considered pioneers of cellular and humoral immunology (Gordon 2008). Pathogen sensing is a key feature of macrophages. Infectious agents are recognized through pathogen recognition receptors (PRRs) that are activated by pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs). This activation leads to a signaling

cascade that allows for the production and release of cytokines and chemokines which in turn recruit and activate a range of additional immune cells (Grigoryeva and Cianciotto 2021). PRRs include Toll-like receptors (TLRs), RIG-I-like receptors (RLRs), Nod-like receptors (NLRs), AIM2-like receptors (ALRs), C-type lectin receptors (CLRs), and intracellular DNA sensors such as cGAS (Kawasaki and Kawai 2014).

Macrophages are present in almost all tissues, but their origin is mainly linked to monocytes, which migrate to peripheral tissues and differentiate into macrophages as needed. Interestingly, there have been reports and evidence that support the hypothesis that some macrophages originate from the yolk sack during embryogenesis and are maintained independently of monocytes (Yona and Gordon 2015). In addition, some tissues have macrophages with unique tissue-specific functions, such as microglia, bone osteoclasts, alveolar mac-

rophages, and Kupffer cells, that could be considered separate classes of macrophages (Ross et al. 2021). More than a century after the discovery of macrophages, there are still some uncertainties regarding their origin, phenotype, and functions, which are due to the cells' great plasticity to accommodate their many functions under both physiological and pathological conditions. This article provides an overview of the different phenotypes macrophages can adopt in response to different stimuli and pathogens.

MACROPHAGES: THE CONCEPT OF CELL POLARIZATION

The concept of macrophage polarity is still controversial. Macrophage classification is adapted mainly for *in vitro* research and an easier understanding of different macrophage activation states in response to various factors. *In vivo*, macrophages adopt and modify their functional phenotypes in response to continuous changes in the tissue microenvironment (Strizova et al. 2023). Therefore, although not ideal, macrophage taxonomy is useful in systematically classifying and describing the complexity and adaptability of mononuclear phagocytes. According to their basic functions, macrophages are divided into two populations – M1, pro-inflammatory or classically activated macrophages, and M2, immunoregulatory and wound healing, or alternatively activated macrophages (Mantovani et al. 2004; Martinez et al. 2008; Mosser and Edwards 2008). The M1/M2 classification of macrophages mirrors Th1/2 nomenclature, and it might lead us to believe that T cells are instructing macrophage polarization, but on the contrary, macrophages are the cells that can initiate and direct T-cell responses as the adaptive immune response is triggered by innate immunity (Viola et al. 2019). The M1/M2 classification of macrophages can be viewed as a framework representing a continuum of different functional states, of which M1 and M2 activation states represent the extremes (Martinez and Gordon 2014).

M1/M2 MACROPHAGES: *IN VITRO* MODELS AND PHENOTYPING

In vitro models of human macrophages can be generated from CD14⁺ monocytes isolated from human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) after a 7-day stimulation with colony-stimulating factors (CSF). M1 primed macrophages are generated with granulocyte macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF) in a complete RPMI medium and the M2 phenotype is promoted with macrophage colony-stimulating factor (M-CSF) (Lukic, Larssen et al. 2017). General M1/M2 stimuli and phenotyping markers for human M1/M2 monocyte-derived macrophages are included in Figure 1 and Table 1. As both cell types originate from the same

cell precursor, substantial overlap between molecular markers is expected, and one must include surface, cellular, and secretory molecular targets in a phenotyping panel.

Primed macrophages are activated towards the full M1 pro-inflammatory phenotype by subsequent incubation with LPS or inflammation-related cytokines TNF- α or IFN- γ , alone or in combination (Mantovani et al. 2004). These cells are detected as IL-12^{high}, IL-23^{high} and IL-10^{low} secreting cells with high surface expression of MHC class II molecules, positive for CD68 (monocyte and macrophage marker), CD80 and CD86 (both are ligands to the costimulatory molecule CD28 on the surface of all naïve T cells). To kill pathogens and initiate an inflammatory immune response, these cells produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitric oxide (NO) as toxic effector molecules and inflammatory cytokines IL-12, IL-23, IL-6, TNF α , and IL-1. Expression of genes responsible for M1 differentiation and function is under the tight control of transcription factors and post-translational regulators activated by IFNs and TLR signaling, including STAT1, STAT5, IRF3, IRF5 and NF- κ B (Italiani and Boraschi 2014; Labonte et al. 2014). M1 macrophages also secrete large amounts of functional activin A, a growth and differentiation factor that promotes the expression of M1 markers and down-regulates IL-10 (Sierra-Filardi et al. 2011).

Contrarily to the M1 phenotype, the M2 phenotype has quickly expanded to three subtypes: M2a, M2b and M2c (Table 1). There is also a fourth class of M2s, labeled

Fig. 1. Activation of resting-state macrophages, M0, towards M1 or M2 phenotype (M2a-M2c sub-phenotypes) is governed by different stimuli. IC- immune complexes; TLR/IL-1R L- TLR/IL-1R ligands.

Table 1. M1/M2 stimuli and phenotyping markers for human M1/M2 monocyte-derived macrophages.

Macrophage type	<i>In vitro</i> stimuli	Surface markers	Cellular markers	Secreted cytokines and other reactive molecules	Function
M1 (classical)	LPS, TNF- α , IFN γ , GM-CSF	CD80, CD86, TLR2&4, MHC II ^{high} , IFN γ R	CD68, NF- κ B, STAT1&5, IRF3&5, iNOS	IL-12, IL-23, IL-6, TNF α , IL-1, ROS, NO	Th1 responses, killing pathogens, tumor resistance
M2 (alternative):					
M2a	IL-4 and IL-13	CD163, CD200, Dectin-1, MHC II ^{low} , mannose receptor (MR, CD206), SRs (scavenger receptors A & B1)	IRF4, PPAR γ , STAT6, Arginase-1	IL-10, IL-1R α , TGF β , IL-12, polyamines	Th2 responses, allergy, killing pathogens
M2b	Immune complexes and TLR/IL-1R ligands	CD86, MHC II ^{low}	IRF4, SOCS3	IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-10 ^{high} , IL-12 ^{low} , TNF α	Th 2 activation, immunoregulation
M2c	IL-10, TGF β , glucocorticoids	CD163, CD206, TLR1	IRF4, SOCS3	IL-10, TGF β , extracellular matrix proteoglycan- versican	Immunoregulation, tissue remodeling

Sources: Mantovani et al. 2004; Gordon and Taylor 2005; Labonte et al. 2014; Martinez and Gordon 2014; Lukic et al. 2017.

M2d, which represents tumor-associated macrophages, or TAMs which are known to promote cancer invasion (Wu et al. 2012). M2a is activated by IL-4 or IL-13, M2b by immune complexes and TLR ligands or IL-1R agonists, and M2c by glucocorticoids or IL-10. In general, alternatively activated macrophages are regarded as IL-10 secreting macrophages with an anti-inflammatory profile, allowing for inflammation resolution and tissue repair. They express high levels of the mannose receptor and C-type lectin receptors (CD206, CD209, and Dectin-1 to name a few) and scavenger receptors (CD163) and produce pro-fibrotic factors such as TGF β (Mantovani et al. 2013). Furthermore, the intracellular markers and effectors linked to M2 polarization encompass STAT6, SOCS3 (suppressor of cytokine signaling 3), PPAR γ (peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma), and arginase-1 (Italiani and Boraschi 2014).

Polarized macrophages have differential metabolic features that are closely related to their function. M1 stimuli shift glucose metabolism towards the anaerobic glycolytic pathway as they need a quick energy supply and performance under a hypoxic tissue microenvironment. On the contrary, M2 polarization-related tissue remodeling actions require a continuous energy supply as achieved via oxidative glucose metabolism (Rodríguez-Prados et al. 2010). Investigations in mouse and human macrophages show that iron metabolism differs significantly between M1- and M2-polarized cells (Corna et al. 2010; Recalcati et al. 2010). M1 macrophages display large levels of iron storage proteins such as ferritin,

whereas M2 macrophages express low levels of ferritin but high levels of ferroportin (iron exporter). This differential iron metabolism has been linked to their functional outcomes. Interestingly, the major metabolic difference between the two cell phenotypes is in the conversion of arginine. In M2 macrophages, it results in the production of ornithine and polyamines, but in M1 cells, it leads to the generation of citrulline and NO (Qualls et al. 2012). Production of ornithine can enhance cellular proliferation and promote wound healing by facilitating the biosynthesis of polyamines and collagen. Moreover, previous studies have established a correlation between ornithine and fibrosis, as well as other processes related to tissue remodeling (Pesce et al. 2009). It is noteworthy to add that the synthesis of polyamines has been discovered to autonomously induce M2 polarization (Van den Bossche et al. 2012). Overall, metabolic adaptability plays an important role in macrophage polarization and functional diversity.

MACROPHAGE POLARIZATION IN INFECTIOUS DISEASES

Following stimulation with microbiological products, macrophages can acquire enhanced microbicidal capabilities. M1 macrophages are often linked to disease protection and help the body get rid of bacteria including *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Mycobacterium ulcerans*, and *Chlamydia* (Benoit et al. 2008).

However, some pathogenic bacteria, particularly intracellular species, have evolved strategies to redirect and modify macrophage activation to increase their survival. Paciello and colleagues (2013), found that the intracellular form of *Shigella flexneri* produces an altered, hypoacetylated form of LPS that evades recognition by TLR4 and induces decreased production of proinflammatory cytokines from murine bone marrow-derived macrophages. Bacteria *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* subverted the inflammatory response in infected mice by stimulating Wnt6 signaling in lung macrophages, thereby promoting M2-like polarization (Schaale et al. 2013). Biofilms of *Staphylococcus aureus* were resistant to macrophage invasion in a mouse model of catheter-associated biofilm infections; however, some macrophages that effectively invaded the biofilm exhibited decreased IL-1, TNF α , and iNOS expression but robust arginase-1 expression, indicative of an M2 profile (Thurlow et al. 2011). *Salmonella* strains have an interesting mechanism of infection. They shift the macrophage phenotype to M2 by driving noncanonical activation of STAT3 and by upregulating PPAR δ , a transcription factor that forces a lipid oxidation metabolism in the cell leaving more glucose available for the bacteria (Eisele et al. 2013; Taylor and Winter 2020).

In contrast to bacterial pathogens, which typically flourish within and promote the production of M2 macrophages, viral pathogens tend to have a more complex relationship with macrophages. Some viruses induce macrophage polarization toward the M1 phenotype (Avian influenza A H5N1 (Zhang et al. 2018), Foot and mouth disease virus (FMDV) (Sebastian et al. 2020)), while others promote M2 polarization (SARS-CoV-2 (Boumaza et al. 2021)). Moreover, several viruses induce complex macrophage phenotypes depending on viral strains, infection stages, and even the gender of the host (Yu et al. 2022). For example, the relationship between human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) and macrophage polarization. HCMV encodes a homolog of human IL-10 (product of the viral gene UL111A), so the virus is capable of polarizing monocytes towards the M2 phenotype to repress the host immune response required for replication (Avdic et al. 2013). Despite this, it has been shown that HCMV-activated macrophages acquire an M1 transcriptome profile (Chan et al. 2008). It seems that upon infection in monocytes, HCMV drives their acquisition of a unique mixed-mode macrophage phenotype by upregulating selected M1 and M2 differentiation markers, via a non-canonical activation of the Akt signaling network (Cojohari et al. 2020).

The human immunodeficiency virus, HIV, appears to gain an advantage from the M2 polarization. HIV-1 exhibits impaired or delayed infection of M1 macrophages with multiple issues in the entry and post-entry steps (Cassetta et al. 2013), but M2 macrophages express a surface recep-

tor DC-SIGN which facilitates HIV-1 entry, DNA synthesis, and transmission from infected macrophages to CD4+ T cells (Cassol et al. 2013). Notably, it was also reported that HIV-1 clathrin-mediated endocytosis is increased in M1 and decreased in M2 macrophages (Gobeil et al. 2012). However, this type of endocytosis results in increased viral degradation rather than productive infection. Like HCMV, HIV-1 can induce macrophage polarization. HIV-1 drives macrophages toward M1 polarization and stimulates an M2-to-M1 transition (Lugo-Villarino et al. 2011). These contradictions are quite useful for the virus, M2 macrophages are used as a reservoir of replication and M1 macrophages recruit new immune cells and disseminate the infection.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The involvement of M1 and M2 macrophages is evident in several stages of infection, including early, late, and chronic phases, as well as in the pathogenesis of other conditions not mentioned here, such as allergies, diabetes, and malignancies. In the fight against the immune-system invaders, the host seeks to eradicate the invading pathogens by activating the M1 macrophages, which induce an inflammatory response. Subsequently, the host aims to promote tissue repair and mitigate the immunological response by engaging M2 macrophages among other cells. As the functional phenotype of macrophages can be influenced by both innate and adaptive immune signals, a lack of adequate regulation can lead to potentially harmful outcomes. For example, uncontrolled actions of the M1 macrophages can induce tissue damage and affect glucose metabolism. Conversely, M2 macrophages can be utilized by pathogens as a means of facilitating intracellular survival. In the long competitive history between viruses and hosts, viruses have evolved various immune evasion strategies that interfere with the M1/M2 resolution of infections. Therefore, studying the biology of these intriguing cells presents a promising prospect for the future development of therapeutics. In addition, recent trends in immunology (Wu et al. 2022; Kloc et al. 2023) suggest that following the elimination of infectious agents, the macrophage genome retains the immunological memory from the initial encounter which allows for faster and stronger pro-inflammatory response upon a second encounter with the same or different pathogens. Hence, it is most likely that future treatment strategies against some pathogens will be directed towards macrophages, either by inhibiting their migration to areas of inflammation or by modulating their phenotypes from M1 to M2, or conversely.

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REFERENCES

- Avdic SJZ, Cao BP, McSharry LE, Clancy R, Brown M, Steain DJ, Gottlieb A, Abendroth A, Slobedman B. 2013. Human cytomegalovirus interleukin-10 polarizes monocytes toward a deactivated M2c phenotype to repress host immune responses. *Journal of Virology*. 87(18):10273–10282.
- Benoit M, Desnues B, Mege JL. 2008. Macrophage polarization in bacterial infections. *Journal of Immunology*. 181(6):3733–3739.
- Boumaza A, Gay L, Mezouar S, Bestion E, Diallo AB, Michel B, Desnues D, Raoult D, La Scola B, Halfon P, et al. 2021. Monocytes and macrophages, targets of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2: The clue for coronavirus disease 2019 immunoparalysis. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 224(3):395–406.
- Cassetta L, Kajaste-Rudnitski A, Coradin T, Saba E, Della Chiara G, Barbagallo M, Graziano F, Alfano M, Cassol E, Vicenzi E, et al. 2013. M1 polarization of human monocyte-derived macrophages restricts pre and postintegration steps of HIV-1 replication. *Aids*. 27(12):1847–1856.
- Cassol E, Cassetta L, Rizzi C, Gabuzda D, Alfano M, Poli G. 2013. Dendritic cell-specific intercellular adhesion molecule-3 grabbing nonintegrin mediates HIV-1 infection of and transmission by M2a-polarized macrophages in vitro. *Aids*. 27(5):707–716.
- Chan G, Bivins-Smith ER, Smith MS, Smith PM, Yurochko AD. 2008. Transcriptome analysis reveals human cytomegalovirus reprograms monocyte differentiation toward an M1 macrophage. *Journal of Immunology*. 181(1):698–711.
- Cojohari O, Mahmud J, Altman AM, Peppenelli MA, Miller MJ, Chan GC. 2020. Human cytomegalovirus mediates unique monocyte-to-macrophage differentiation through the PI3K/SHIP1/Akt signaling network. *Viruses*. 12(6):652.
- Corna G, Campana L, Pignatti E, Castiglioni A, Tagliafico E, Bosurgi L, Campanella A, Brunelli S, Manfredi AA, Apostoli P, et al. 2010. Polarization dictates iron handling by inflammatory and alternatively activated macrophages. *Haematologica*. 95(11):1814–1822.
- Eisele NA, Ruby T, Jacobson A, Manzanillo PS, Cox JS, Mukundan LL, Chawla A, Monack DM. 2013. *Salmonella* require the fatty acid regulator PPAR δ for the establishment of a metabolic environment essential for long-term persistence. *Cell Host and Microbe*. 14(2):171–182.
- Gobeil LA, Lodge R, Tremblay MJ. 2012. Differential HIV-1 endocytosis and susceptibility to virus infection in human macrophages correlate with cell activation status. *Journal of Virology*. 86(19):10399–10407.
- Gordon S. 2008. Elie Metchnikoff: father of natural immunity. *European Journal of Immunology*. 38(12):3257–3264.
- Gordon S, Taylor PR. 2005. Monocyte and macrophage heterogeneity. *Nature Reviews Immunology*. 5(12):953–964.
- Grigoryeva LS, Cianciotto NP. 2021. Human macrophages utilize a wide range of pathogen recognition receptors to recognize *Legionella pneumophila*, including Toll-Like Receptor 4 engaging *Legionella* lipopolysaccharide and the Toll-like Receptor 3 nucleic-acid sensor. *PLOS Pathogens*. 17(7):e1009781.
- Italiani P, Boraschi D. 2014. From monocytes to M1/M2 macrophages: Phenotypical vs. functional differentiation. *Frontier in Immunology*. 5:514.
- Kawasaki T, Kawai T. 2014. Toll-Like Receptor signaling pathways. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 5:511.
- Kloc M, Kubiak JZ, Zdanowski R, Ghobrial RM. 2023. Memory macrophages. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 24(1):38.
- Labonte AC, Tosello-Tramont AC, Hahn YS. 2014. The role of macrophage polarization in infectious and inflammatory diseases. *Molecular Cells*. 37(4):275–285.
- Lugo-Villarino G, Verollet C, Maridonneau-Parini I, Neyrolles O. 2011. Macrophage polarization: convergence point targeted by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and HIV. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2:43.
- Lukic A, Larssen P, Fauland A, Samuelsson B, Wheelock CE, Gabriellson S, Radmark O. 2017. GM-CSF- and M-CSF-primed macrophages present similar resolving but distinct inflammatory lipid mediator signatures. *FASEB Journal*. 31(10):4370–4381.
- Mantovani A, Biswas SK, Galdiero MR, Sica A, Locati M. 2013. Macrophage plasticity and polarization in tissue repair and remodelling. *Journal of Pathology*. 229(2):176–185.
- Mantovani A, Sica A, Sozzani S, Allavena P, Vecchi A, Locati M. 2004. The chemokine system in diverse forms of macrophage activation and polarization. *Trends in Immunology*. 25(12):677–686.
- Martinez FO, Gordon S. 2014. The M1 and M2 paradigm of macrophage activation: time for reassessment. *F1000 Prime Reports*. 6:13.
- Martinez FO, Sica A, Mantovani A, Locati M. 2008. Macrophage activation and polarization. *Frontiers in Bioscience*. 13:453–461.
- Mosser DM, Edwards JP. 2008. Exploring the full spectrum of macrophage activation. *Nature Review Immunology*. 8(12):958–969.
- Paciello I, Silipo A, Lembo-Fazio L, Curcurù L, Zumsteg A, Noèl G, Ciancarella V, Sturiale L, Molinaro A, Bernardini ML. 2013. Intracellular *Shigella* remodels its LPS to dampen the innate immune recognition and evade inflammasome activation. *Proceedings of National Academy of Sciences USA*. 110(46):E4345–4354.
- Pesce JT, Ramalingam TR, Mentink-Kane MM, Wilson MS, El Kasmi KC, Smith AM, Thompson RW, Cheever AW, Murray PJ, Wynn TA. 2009. Arginase-1-expressing macrophages suppress Th2 cytokine-driven inflammation and fibrosis. *PLoS Pathogens*. 5(4):e1000371.
- Qualls JE, Subramanian C, Rafi W, Smith AM, Balouzian L, DeFreitas AA, Shirey KA, Reutterer B, Kernbauer E, Stockinger S, et al. 2012. Sustained generation of nitric oxide and control of mycobacterial infection requires argininosuccinate synthase 1. *Cell Host & Microbe*. 12(3):313–323.
- Recalcatti S, Locati M, Marini A, Santambrogio P, Zaninotto F, De Pizzol M, Zammataro L, Girelli D, Cairo G. 2010. Differential regulation of iron homeostasis during human macrophage polarized activation. *European Journal of Immunology*. 40(3):824–835.
- Rodríguez-Prados JC, Través PG, Cuenca J, Rico D, Aragonés J, Martín-Sanz P, Cascante M, Boscá L. 2010. Substrate fate in activated macrophages: a comparison between innate, classic, and alternative activation. *Journal of Immunology*. 185(1):605–614.
- Ross EA, Devitt A, Johnson JR. 2021. Macrophages: The good, the bad, and the gluttony. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 12:708186.
- Schaale K, Brandenburg J, Kispert A, Leites M, Ehlers S, Reiling N. 2013. Wnt6 is expressed in granulomatous lesions of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*-infected mice and is involved in macrophage differentiation and proliferation. *Journal of Immunology*. 191(10):5182–5195.
- Sebastian R, Sravanthi M, Umaphathi V, Krishnaswamy N, Priyanka M, Dechamma HJ, Ganesh K, Basagoudanavar SH, Sanyal A, Reddy GR. 2020. Foot and mouth disease virus undergoes non-progressive replication in mice peritoneal macrophages and induces M1 polarization. *Virus Research*. 281:197906.
- Sierra-Filardi E, Puig-Kröger A, Blanco FJ, Nieto C, Bragado R, Palomero MI, Bernabéu C, Vega MA, Corbí AL. 2011. Activin A skews macrophage polarization by promoting a proinflammatory phenotype and inhibiting the acquisition of anti-inflammatory macrophage markers. *Blood*. 117(19): 5092–5101.
- Strizova Z, Benesova I, Bartolini R, Novyzedlak R, Ceceřdlova E, Foley LK, Striz I. 2023. M1/M2 macrophages and their overlaps - myth or reality? *Clinical Science (London)*. 137(15):1067–1093.
- Taylor SJ, Winter SE. 2020. *Salmonella* finds a way: Metabolic versatility of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium in diverse host environments. *PLOS Pathogens*. 16(6):e1008540.
- Thurlow LR, Hanke ML, Fritz T, Angle A, Aldrich A, Williams SH, Engbrechtsen IL, Bayles KW, Horswill AR, Kielian T. 2011. *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms prevent macrophage phagocytosis and attenuate inflammation in vivo. *Journal of Immunology*. 186(11):6585–6596.

- Van den Bossche J, Lamers WH, Koehler ES, Geuns JM, Alhonen L, Uimari A, Pirnes-Karhu S, Van Overmeire E, Morias Y, Brys L, et al. 2012. Pivotal Advance: Arginase-1-independent polyamine production stimulates the expression of IL-4-induced alternatively activated macrophage markers while inhibiting LPS-induced expression of inflammatory genes. *Journal of Leukocyte Biology*. 91(5):685–699.
- Viola A, Munari F, Sánchez-Rodríguez R, Scolaro T, Castegna A. 2019. The metabolic signature of macrophage responses. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 10:1462.
- Wu C, Xu Y, Zhao Y. 2022. Two kinds of macrophage memory: innate and adaptive immune-like macrophage memory. *Cellular and Molecular Immunology*. 19(7):852–854.
- Wu H, Xu JB, He YL, Peng JJ, Zhang XH, Chen CQ, Li W, Cai SR. 2012. Tumor-associated macrophages promote angiogenesis and lymphangiogenesis of gastric cancer. *Journal of Surgical Oncology*. 106(4):462–468.
- Yona S, Gordon S. 2015. From the reticuloendothelial to mononuclear phagocyte system - the unaccounted years. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 6:328.
- Yu S, Ge H, Li S, Qiu HJ. 2022. Modulation of macrophage polarization by viruses: turning off/on host antiviral responses. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 13:839585
- Zhang N, Bao YJ, Tong AH, Zuyderduyn S, Bader GD, Malik Peiris JS, Lok S, Lee SM. 2018. Whole transcriptome analysis reveals a differential gene expression profile reflecting macrophage polarization in response to influenza A H5N1 virus infection. *BMC Medical Genomics*. 11(1):20.